

Solvent Extraction Studies of Metals with Chelating Agents and High Molecular Weight Carboxylic Acids

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Extensive solvent extraction studies of metals—transitional and non-transitional have been carried out in the author's laboratories. Both chelate and ion-association extraction systems have been critically investigated with respect to the relevant experimental parameters and numerous practical analytical procedure developed on the basis of such studies. The extraction equilibria for some of the important extraction systems have been studied which give an insight into the probable nature and composition of the extracted species. The review article summarizes the work done on equilibrium studies in TTA systems and extraction of metals with High Molecular Weight Carboxylic acids.

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It is well-known that solvent extraction is probably the most versatile of all analytical techniques in that it has an extremely wide range of application and calls for most of the physicochemical principles used generally in analytical chemistry. It has therefore considerable theoretical as well as practical importance

*Nature of the extractable species*¹⁻³

An important aspect of Solvent extraction chemistry is to elucidate the species in which the solute occurs in the two phases and their relative stability. In some cases this information is available from independent measurements for one phase and inference is drawn for the other from distribution measurements only. Anyway it is desirable to have a detailed knowledge of the extracted species in the organic phase.

There are two principal factors which cause the distribution to favour the organic phase: a low

affinity of the solute for the aqueous and a high affinity, for the organic phase. Affinity consists of total interaction energy which is the sum total of solvation energy, electrostatic interaction energy among ions, dipole-interaction energy, hole-formation energy, entropy factors etc.

Qualitatively, a species will have a low affinity for the aqueous phase provided it meets the following requirements:

- (i) Zero or low charge—Hydration of ions increases rapidly with increasing charge.
- (ii) Large size—Hydration of ions decreases and hole formation energy increases with increasing size.
- (iii) Non-polar nature—The lower the polarity of a molecule, the less its interaction with water dipoles.
- (iv) Absence of electronegative atoms at the surface—Hydrogen bonding to water does not take place in absence of electronegative atoms at the surface of the species.
- (v) Low water activity—Salting-out agents decrease the availability of water for interaction with the solute.

The same factors are also responsible for a high affinity of the solute for the organic phase.

*Equilibrium studies in TTA Systems*²⁶⁻²⁷

2-Thenoyltrifluoroacetone (TTA) has been used in this laboratory for the extraction of numerous

metals⁴⁻²⁵ including chromium, molybdenum and tungsten. The reaction products were previously considered to be chromium(III)-TTA, molybdenum(VI)-TTA and tungsten(VI)-TTA chelates, but these were not confirmed experimentally.

In the present work the nature and composition of the metal-TTA chelates have been investigated by spectrophotometric methods by measuring the distribution ratio of the metals as functions of TTA and hydrogen ion concentrations following the methods of Onishi et al and Connick and McVey. In some cases the composition of the chelates has been verified by Job's method. The nature of the ionic chelates have been confirmed by ion-exchange behaviour of the chelates. The extraction coefficients of TTA between two phases under the experimental conditions have been determined following a modified method of De et al which is a definite improvement over the method of Akaza et al. The extraction constants of the metal-TTA complexes have also been determined.

The nature and compositions of the TTA chelates of chromium, molybdenum and tungsten were studied in hydrochloric and sulphuric acid media. In general it was found that the sulphate complexes of these metals are more stable than the corresponding chloro complexes, and better extractions were obtained from aqueous hydrochloric acid solutions. These results are concordant with the reports. Variation of D_M ($M=Cr, Mo, W$) with hydrogen ion concentration from $5.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ — $10.0 M$ hydrochloric acid and from $5.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ — $5.0 M$ sulphuric acid at $1.5 \times 10^{-1} M$ TTA concentration in appropriate organic phase were plotted. D_{Cr} has maximum values at $1.0 M$ hydrochloric acid and at $5.0 \times 10^{-1} M$ sulphuric acid concentrations whereas D_{Mo} and D_W have maximum values at $>6.0 \times 10^{-1} M$ and $>5.82 M$ hydrochloric acid and at $5.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ and $3.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ sulphuric acid concentrations respectively.

Since molybdenum(VI) is extracted into polar solvents (e.g. ethyl ether, isopropyl ether or amyl acetate) as the chloro complex from hydrochloric acid solution the extraction behaviour of molybdenum(VI) and also of tungsten(VI) from aqueous hydrochloric acid into n-butanol-acetophenone (1:1 by volume) and n-butanol-acetophenone (2:3 by volume) respectively were studied in the absence of TTA. The extraction of molybdenum(VI) as the chloro complex from aqueous $6.0 \times 10^{-1} M$ hydrochloric acid solution is not significant in absence of TTA ($D=0.20$ cf. $D=110$ in presence of TTA) while tungsten(VI) shows significant extraction from $5.0 M$ hydro-

chloric acid solution ($D=1.8$ cf. $D=\sim 10^2$ in the presence of TTA). It seems probable that at higher hydrochloric acid concentrations tungsten(VI) chloro complex is being replaced by tungsten(VI)-TTA chelate in the presence of TTA.

In order to explore the compositions of the TTA-chelates of chromium, molybdenum and tungsten extracted from aqueous hydrochloric and sulphuric acid solutions, variation of D_M ($M=Cr, Mo, W$) with the concentrations of TTA in the respective organic phases were studied at constant hydrogen ion concentrations in the aqueous phases. For this TTA concentration were varied from $2.0 \times 10^{-1} M$ — $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ at $1.0 M$ hydrochloric acid and at $5.0 \times 10^{-1} M$ sulphuric acid in the case of chromium ($Cr=9.5 \times 10^{-6} M$) and in the case of molybdenum and tungsten, TTA concentration was varied from $2.0 \times 10^{-1} M$ — $3.16 \times 10^{-3} M$ at $6.0 \times 10^{-1} M$ and $5.6 M$ hydrochloric acid and at $5.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ sulphuric acid concentration respectively (molybdenum= $2.08 \times 10^{-6} M$ tungsten = $1.8 \times 10^{-6} M$). In the case of extractions from hydrochloric acid solutions the slopes of $\log D_M - \log (TTA)_0$ are 3.2, 2.3 and 2.3 for chromium, molybdenum and tungsten respectively, while those in the case of extractions from sulphuric acid solutions are 1.1, 3.6 and 3.1 for chromium, molybdenum and tungsten respectively. These results indicate the formation of CrT_3 , MoO_2T_2 and WO_2T_2 (HT=enol form of TTA) in the organic phase from aqueous hydrochloric acid solutions and the formation of $H_2CrT(SO_4)_2$, $HMoO_2T_3$ and HWO_2T_3 in the organic phase from aqueous sulphuric acid solutions. The anionic nature of the species was verified by absorbing the chelates in the anion exchange resin (Amberlite IRA 400, Cl⁻ form) previously saturated with the respective solvent. The anions were eluted with acetone, n-butanol-acetophenone (1:1) and n-butanol-acetophenone (2:3) respectively preequilibrated with $5.0 \times 10^{-1} M$, $5.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ and $5.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ sulphuric acid respectively in the cases of chromium, molybdenum and tungsten. From the effluent tests for chromium, molybdenum and tungsten respectively were obtained. In order to check the presence of SO_4^{2-} in the chromium (III)-TTA chelate extracted from aqueous sulphuric acid, the organic phase after careful separation was allowed to evaporate, digested with fuming nitric acid and tested for SO_4^{2-} which gave positive results. Furthermore, the composition of the species extracted from aqueous sulphuric acid solutions were confirmed by following Job's method. The M-TTA ratios are 1:1, 1:3, and 1:3 for chromium, molybdenum and tungsten respectively. In these experiments equimolar solutions of metal ion and TTA were used.

The dependence of D_{Cr} on TTA concentration in the organic phase was determined in the pH range 3.75-6.50. D_{Cr} has maximum value (∞) at pH 5.55 and above or below this pH D_{Cr} decreases. Acetic acid-ammonium acetate buffer solution was used at pH 3.75-6.50. From the experimental results the slope, $\log D_{Cr} - \log(HT)_o$ was calculated. The results are shown in Table 1. Within the pH range 3.75-5.32, the slope varies from 2.70-3.25 and at pH 5.55, the slope is 2.90 which indicates the formation of CrT_3 in the organic phase within the pH range 3.75-5.55. But at pH 6.50 the slope decreases to 2.10 indicating that the probable species in the organic phase is $[CrT_2(OH)(H_2O)]$.

To check these results, the dependence of D_{Cr} on hydrogen ion concentration was investigated at pH 3.20-5.30 and at pH 5.80-7.50. In this experiment, the concentration of chromium in the aqueous phase was $9.5 \times 10^{-6} M$. At pH 3.20-5.30, the slope is 3.1 and at pH 5.80-7.50, the slope is -2.2. These results are concordant with the results of the above experiment.

TABLE 1—SLOPE OF EXTRACTION CURVES AT VARIOUS PH

pH equilibrium	$[HT]_o, M$	Log $D_{Cr} - \log [HT]_o$
3.75	$1.5 \times 10^{-1} - 6.0 \times 10^{-3}$	2.70
4.02	$1.0 \times 10^{-1} - 5.0 \times 10^{-3}$	2.65
4.63	$6.0 \times 10^{-2} - 5.0 \times 10^{-3}$	2.80
5.32	$8.0 \times 10^{-2} - 2.5 \times 10^{-3}$	3.25
6.50	$1.5 \times 10^{-1} - 8.0 \times 10^{-3}$	2.10

Distribution ratio of TTA

In order to obtain the distribution ratio of TTA between organic and aqueous phases ($[TTA]_o/[TTA]_a$), under various conditions, the concentrations of TTA in the aqueous phase after equilibration with the organic phase and in some cases the concentrations of TTA in the organic phase after equilibration were determined by a modified spectrophotometric method of De and Khopkar using the iron(III)-TTA complex. In this respect attempts to follow the method due to Akaza et al did not give encouraging results. It was rather difficult to dissolve TTA in pH 3 buffer (KCl-HCl) and secondly, iron(III) at milligram level could not be kept in solution at pH 3. Accordingly, it was thought desirable to modify the method of Akaza to suit our purpose.

The results are shown in Table 2. It may be mentioned that the distribution ratio obtained by Onishi et al is 60 in a 0.5 M sulphuric acid-xylene system, whereas the value is 58.8 as obtained from our measurements.

Extraction constant

The extraction constant, K , for various TTA-chelates of chromium, molybdenum and tungsten were calculated. The results are shown in Table 3.

Extraction with High Molecular Weight Carboxylic Acid

There are several reports in the literature on the extraction of metals with the aid of carboxylic acids. Fletcher et al²⁸⁻³⁰ worked with commercially available naphthenic acids and with versatic acids. Sptizer et al³¹ studied the extraction behaviour of iron(III), cobalt(II) and copper(II) with versatic acid. In our laboratory systematic studies of solvent extraction behaviour of some di, tri and tetravalent metals with versatic acids (namely, SRS-100, Versatic-9) has been carried out. SRS-100 and Versatic-9 are synthetic carboxylic acids prepared from C_{15} - and C_9 -olefines. Versatic-9 is a mixture of highly branched saturated aliphatic acids containing nine carbon atoms (C_9) while SRS-100 consists of approximately 50% highly branched predominantly tertiary, high molecular weight versatic acid (C_{15}) and approximately 50% neutral oil. Both the cation-exchangers are soluble in organic solvent. These liquid ion-exchangers have been used for the extraction studies of a number of transition and non-transition³²⁻³⁵ metals. The extraction of a metal ion with a high molecular weight carboxylic acid may be considered to proceed in a manner analogous to the reaction of a metal ion with a cation exchange resin. The extraction equilibrium expression may be written :

General procedure :

A suitable aliquot of the test solution containing about 10 mg of the metal ion under investigation was mixed in a 250 ml separatory funnel with 10 ml appropriate buffer solution. In case of thallium, thallous(I) was oxidised to thallic(III) with bromine water, and the excess bromine was removed by warming the solution before mixing with the buffer solution. Antimony, bismuth and lanthanum tend to hydrolyse at higher pH. In the case of bismuth and lanthanum

TABLE 2—DISTRIBUTION RATIO OF TTA UNDER VARIOUS CONDITIONS

Extraction condition		Period of extraction (min)	D _{TTA}
Aqueous phase	Organic phase		
5.0 × 10 ⁻¹ M HCl	1.5 × 10 ⁻¹ M TTA-n-butanol-acetophenone (1:1)	10	98*
5.0 × 10 ⁻² M H ₂ SO ₄	1.5 × 10 ⁻¹ M TTA-n-butanol-acetophenone (1:1)	10	87*
pH 2.0	1.5 × 10 ⁻¹ M TTA-n-butanol-acetophenone (1:1)	10	96*
5.0 M HCl	1.5 × 10 ⁻¹ M TTA-n-butanol-acetophenone (1:1)	10	205*
5.0 × 10 ⁻² M H ₂ SO ₄	1.5 × 10 ⁻¹ M TTA-n-butanol-acetophenone (1:1)	10	263
pH 5.32	1.5 × 10 ⁻¹ M TTA-benzene	15	19
1.0 M HCl	1.5 × 10 ⁻¹ M TTA-benzene	15	49
5.0 × 10 ⁻¹ M H ₂ SO ₄	1.5 × 10 ⁻¹ M TTA-benzene	15	48
5.0 M HCl	1.5 × 10 ⁻¹ M TTA-benzene	15	57
pH 6.50	1.5 × 10 ⁻¹ M TTA-benzene	15	11

*TTA concentrations in the aqueous phases were determined.

TTA concentrations in both the aqueous and organic phases were measured. The distribution ratio of TTA in a 0.115 M hydrochloric acid-benzene system obtained by King and Reas is 40.

Note: Since TTA is more soluble in acetophenone D_{TTA} increases with the increase in the acetophenone concentration in the mixed solvent.

TABLE 3—EXTRACTION CONSTANT

Extracted species	Aqueous phase	[H] _a , M	[HT] _o , M	K*
[CrT ₃]	Acetic acid-ammonium acetate (1 M) pH 5.32	1.0 × 10 ^{-5.32}	1.395 × 10 ⁻¹	9.7 × 10 ⁻¹³
(CrT ₃ (OH)H ₂ O]	Acetate (1 M) pH 6.50	1.0 × 10 ^{-6.5}	1.375 × 10 ⁻¹	8.5 × 10 ⁻¹⁷
H ₂ [CrT(SO ₄) ₂]	Sulphuric acid	5.0 × 10 ⁻¹	1.47 × 10 ⁻¹	6.7
[CrT ₃]	Hydrochloric acid	1.0	1.47 × 10 ⁻¹	62.7
[MoO ₂ T ₂]	Hydrochloric acid	5.0 × 10 ⁻¹	1.485 × 10 ⁻¹	9.6 × 10 ⁴
H[MoO ₂ T ₂]	Hydrochloric acid	5.0 × 10 ⁻²	1.485 × 10 ⁻¹	4.4 × 10 ⁸
[WO ₂ T ₂]	Hydrochloric acid	5.0	1.49 × 10 ⁻¹	5.2 × 10 ⁸
H[WO ₂ T ₂]	Sulphuric acid	5.0 × 10 ⁻²	1.495 × 10 ⁻¹	5.6 × 10 ⁴

$$K^* = D_M \frac{[M]_a^n}{[HT]_o^n} \text{ where } n = \text{valence of } M.$$

Note: The difference in the K values for the same type of chelate is primarily due to the hydrogen ion concentrations in the aqueous phases and also to the difference in the values of D_M under the conditions used.

this was avoided by carrying out extraction in presence of citrate as masking agents. The appropriate quantities of masking agents were introduced to the experimental solutions before mixing with the buffer solution. Extraction studies of antimony have been carried out by the gradual neutralisation technique³⁴. The pH of the solution was adjusted as desired and extracted with 10 ml. solvent by shaking for 5 minutes, using benzene as diluent (solvent : benzene = 1:2). Only in case of iron(III), the extraction was carried out with 10 ml pure solvent. In such case the volume of the aqueous phase was made 15 ml and that

of the organic phase 10 ml. After complete extraction the two phases were allowed to settle. The aqueous phase was then separated and the equilibrium pH was measured. To remove any trace of organic solvent entrained in the separated aqueous phase, the latter was washed with 5 ml benzene. The resulting benzene extract was added to the separated organic phase. The amount of metal ion present in the aqueous phase was estimated by standard methods. The metal ion present in the organic phase was stripped with (2-4N) sulfuric acid and estimated by conventional methods. In case of calcium, strontium,

barium and lead stripping agent used was 3N nitric acid. In case of palladium back extraction was not possible, and the amount of metal ion present in the organic phase was calculated by difference. Cobalt, nickel, manganese, zinc, cadmium, mercury, magnesium, calcium, strontium, barium, lead, palladium, gallium, indium, thallium, bismuth, lanthanum, zirconium and thorium were estimated by complexometric titration with ethylenediamine tetracetic acid. Cerium and copper were estimated iodometrically and antimony was estimated iodimetrically. Iron was estimated volumetrically with potassium dichromate.

Results and Discussion

The extraction behaviour of all the metals were studied with versatic acids over the pH range 1 to 10.5. From the extraction behaviour of these metals it is evident that the percentage extraction increases with the increase of pH, and becomes quantitative at the optimum pH. This is in good agreement with the conclusion drawn from the extraction equilibrium studies.

The recommended optimum conditions of pH for the quantitative extractions are iron(III) pH 3.15, cobalt pH 8.2, nickel pH 8.3, manganese pH 7.9, copper pH 6.1, palladium pH 5.4, lead pH 6.9, zinc pH 7.1, cadmium pH 8.2, barium pH 8.7, calcium and strontium pH 8.8, magnesium pH 9.2, mercury pH 9.8, gallium pH 4.5, indium pH 5.4, thallium pH 6.2, lanthanum pH 8.2, bismuth, pH 7.0, cerium pH 4.3, thorium pH 6.0 and zirconium pH 2.4 with SRS-100. In case of versatic-9 the respective conditions are pH 3.1 for iron(III), pH 8.1 for cobalt, pH 7.5 for nickel, pH 7.5 for manganese, pH 6.3 for copper, pH 6.9 for zinc, pH 7.0 for cadmium, pH 6.2 for lead, pH 6.0 for cerium, pH 6.0 for thorium and pH 2.9 for zirconium. The results show that the difference in extraction of the metals with SRS-100 and versatic-9 are very little, except that the tendency for emulsion formation at higher pH is greater in case of SRS-100. The rate of extraction is more rapid with versatic-9 than with SRS-100. At higher pH (pH > 8.5) Versatic-9 is soluble in the aqueous phase so at higher pH phase separation is not possible in case of versatic-9.

In order to explore the polymerization phenomenon in the extraction system the metal ion concentration was varied from 20-50 mg under the optimum conditions. In this concentration range it was found that the extraction remains virtually unaffected, indicating absence of polymerization.

The nature of diluent was varied from benzene to toluene, xylene, di-isopropyl ether, butanol etc. It was found that in most of the cases xylene and toluene showed a similar type of extraction, but with butanol and di-isopropyl ether the extraction decreases.

The concentration of the solvent (SRS-100 and versatic-9) was varied from 1:2 to 1:9 with benzene as diluent. The nature of extraction of each metal was studied under different solvent concentration. It was found that dilution of solvent lowers the concentration to an appreciable extent. In the case of pure solvent the tendency for emulsion formation increases. To minimise this emulsion tendency, most of the extraction has been carried out using solvent : benzene in a 1:2 ratio. A qualitative selectivity scale of extraction can be drawn from the optimum extraction conditions obtained with SRS-100. The order is as follows :

Extractive Separations and Exchange reactions

The order of extraction of a metal ion with carboxylic acids is the order of relative stabilities of the metal carboxylates. Thus an exchange reaction is possible between a metal carboxylate in hydrocarbon solutions and a more acidic metal in the aqueous phase. The reaction for divalent metal ions may be represented by :

where the metal A is more acidic than the metal B. Thus a solution of cobalt carboxylate (cobalt extracted in the organic phase) exchanges with iron quantitatively in one stage from aqueous solutions, since the difference in the optimum pH condition for iron and cobalt is quite appreciable. The exchange extraction procedure is applied to various metal ion pairs. The results are tabulated in the table 4. In all most all the cases nearly quantitative extraction has been achieved. Exchange extractions are particularly useful in cases such as Cu/Zn, Cu/Cd and Cu/Ni where the co-extraction of the second metal seriously limits extractive separators. The procedure of the exchange reaction is very simple. An aliquot (1.5-2.0 ml.) of the test solution containing (8-20 mg) of metal ion (M_1) was taken and extracted with 10 ml solvent (SRS-100) under the optimum pH condition using

benzene as the diluent in a 1:2 solvent : diluent ratio. The aqueous phase was separated and the metal (M_1) loaded organic phase was equilibrated with 15 ml buffer solution containing the metal (M_2) to be exchanged, the pH of the latter being the optimum value of extraction of the latter metal (M_2). After equilibrium the two phases were allowed to settle and then separated. The metal ion (M_1) present in the aqueous phase was estimated by conventional method. The metal ion (M_2) present in the organic phase was stripped with (2-4N) sulphuric acid and estimated accordingly.

TABLE 4—EXCHANGE REACTIONS AND SEPARATIONS

Initial Organic phase Metal ion (M_1) mg	Aqueous raffinate Metal ion (M_2) mg	Organic Extract	
		Back washed % (M_1)	Extracted % (M_2)
Zn, 15.8	Cu, 8.4	Zn, 99.6	Cu, 99.5
Co, 9.4	Cu, 8.4	Co, 98.7	Cu, 99.03
Cd, 20.5	Cu, 8.4	Ca, 99.0	Cu, 99.5
Ni, 11.6	Cu, 8.4	Ni, 95.0	Cu, 99.3
Mn, 11.3	Cu, 8.4	Mn, 88.0	Cu, 99.5

The extractive separation procedure is very rapid and simple requires only pH control. Iron (12.7 mg) can be separated from cobalt, -nickel, manganese, zinc, copper, cadmium, mercury, magnesium, calcium, strontium, barium, lead, palladium, indium, thallium, cerium and thorium. The interfering anions are citrate, oxalate, tartrate, fluoride and E.D.T.A. Cobalt, manganese, mercury calcium, magnesium, strontium, barium and palladium do not interfere in the extraction of copper. Zirconium has been separated from thorium, tin, lead, palladium, platinum, gallium, indium, thallium, cobalt, nickel, copper, zinc and cadmium. Cerium(IV) has been separated from tin, lead, palladium, platinum, lanthanum, antimony, cobalt, nickel, manganese and zinc. Thorium has been separated from palladium, platinum, molybdenum, tungsten, cobalt, and nickel.

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